

Title: New scheme based on TF-PCA-LDA-WSVM Modeling for Human Activity Recognition in Smart Home

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INTRODUCTION:

Two serious problems affecting the implementation of human activity recognition algorithms have been acknowledged. The first one corresponds to non-informative sequence features. The second is the class imbalance in the training data due to the fact that people do not spend the same amount of time on the different activities. For instance, in daily activity tasks, sleeping is generally done only once a day, while toileting is done several times a day. Consequently, any automated learning system may have difficulties in learning the concept related to the minority class (toileting). This trivially can result in a degradation of the performance of the automated activity classification algorithms.

AIM:

To address these issues, we propose a new scheme based on a combination of temporal features (TF) of activity when the activity is performed with the constructed feature space by the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA). We added the most significant principal components features (PCF) to the set of linear discriminant features (LDF) extracted using LDA. Then, for the classification, we used the Weighted Support Vector Machines (WSVM). For example, The 'Prepare breakfast' and 'Prepare dinner' activities share the same model as they involve the same set of object interactions. These two activities are distinguished by time of taking place, i.e. 'Prepare breakfast' takes place in the morning hours and "Prepare dinner" takes place in the afternoon or evening hours of the day. This contribution shows that a suitable sequence feature set combined with the WSVM classifier achieves good improvement and efficiency over the traditional used methods. The figure 1 describes this methodology.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the proposed activity recognition approach using the feature insertion with temporal feature (TF).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A new TF-PCA-LDA-WSVM scheme has been proposed to recognize ADL from smart home environment. The installed sensors include passive infrared sensors to detect motion at specific areas, reed switches for open/close states of doors and cupboards, and float sensors to measure the toilet being flushed. The sensor data were collected through a base station and labeled according to the corresponding activity. The method shows three merits. First, after feature extraction by PCA and LDA, and restricted to the most significant principal components and linear discriminants features, the training set is reduced, and the prediction accuracy is improved. Second, the weighted SVM classifier setting different cost parameters for each activity was employed in order to handle the imbalanced human activity datasets and shows significant improvement as compared to SVM (with equal costs). In order to evaluate the performance of our proposed approach, a comparison with some state-of-the-art models has been carried out. This consists of Hidden Markov Model (HMM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), SVM and alternative hybrid models such as PCA-WSVM, LDA-WSVM and PCA-LDA-WSVM.

RESULTS:

For the experiments, we use an openly datasets gathered from three houses having different layouts and different number of sensors. The data were collected by a Base-Station and labelled with different annotation tools. Table 2 shows also the number of data per activity in each dataset.

Table 1. List of activities annotated for each dataset and the number of observations of each activity (,).

Dataset	Annotation	Activities
TK26M	Bluetooth headset	Idle ₍₄₆₂₇₎ ; Leaving ₍₂₂₆₁₇₎ ; Toileting ₍₃₈₀₎ ; Showering ₍₂₆₅₎ ; Sleeping ₍₁₁₆₀₁₎ ; Breakfast ₍₁₀₉₎ ; Dinner ₍₃₄₈₎ ; Drink ₍₅₉₎
TK57M	Bluetooth headset	Idle ₍₂₇₃₂₎ ; Leaving ₍₁₁₉₉₃₎ ; Eating ₍₃₇₆₎ ; Toileting ₍₂₄₃₎ ; Showering ₍₁₉₁₎ ; Brush teeth ₍₁₀₂₎ ; Shaving ₍₆₇₎ ; Sleeping ₍₇₇₃₈₎ ; Dressing ₍₁₁₂₎ ; Medication ₍₁₆₎ ; Breakfast ₍₇₃₎ ; Lunch ₍₆₂₎ ; Dinner ₍₂₉₁₎ ; Snack ₍₂₄₎ ; Drink ₍₃₄₎ ; Relax ₍₂₄₃₅₎
OrdonezA	Handwritten diary	Idle ₍₁₃₀₇₎ ; Sleeping ₍₇₈₈₆₎ ; Toileting ₍₁₇₃₎ ; Showering ₍₁₂₁₎ ; Breakfast ₍₁₃₂₎ ; Grooming ₍₁₅₄₎ ; Spare_Time/TV ₍₈₆₄₆₎ ; Leaving ₍₁₆₉₂₎ ; Lunch ₍₃₃₁₎ ; Snack ₍₁₄₎

The results demonstrate that our approach outperforms other methods in terms of F-measure for all datasets. The results show that the combined feature set TF-PCF-LDF contributes to significantly enhance the performance of individual classifier WSVM.

Table 2. F-measure and Accuracy results for all approaches. Bold values are the highest F-Measure for each dataset.

Datasets	Approach	Nb Features	F-measure (%)	Accuracy	
TK26M	Models	HMM	28	79.1	94.5
		KNN	28	71.6	94.4
		SVM	28	67.0	95.5
		WSVM	28	73.7	92.5
	Hybrid Models	PCA-WSVM	6	71.5	91.2
		LDA-WSVM	7	77.7	93.5
		PCA-LDA-WSVM	13	79.4	95.6
		TF-PCA-LDA-WSVM	13	82.4	93.8
TK57M	Models	HMM	42	39.0	76.0
		KNN	42	34.6	79.2
		SVM	42	35.2	80.8
		WSVM	42	39.2	77.1
	Hybrid Models	PCA-WSVM	7	35.3	76.9
		LDA-WSVM	15	41.0	77.2
		PCA-LDA-WSVM	22	44.8	81.4
		TF-PCA-LDA-WSVM	22	47.5	81.0
OrdonezA	Models	HMM	24	61.6	63.7
		KNN	24	56.0	84.2
		SVM	24	59.1	85.2
		WSVM	24	63.9	84.4
	Hybrid Models	PCA-WSVM	4	64.2	84.5
		LDA-WSVM	9	67.0	87.1
		PCA-LDA-WSVM	13	68.2	88.0
		TF-PCA-LDA-WSVM	13	71.8	84.1

CONCLUSION:

From the detailed analysis and comparisons of results, it can be concluded that compared to existing approaches the proposed learning method proves to be more effective and reliable in correct classification of activities in the case of limited amount of training data, variations in activity patterns and frequencies of execution of activities. Furthermore, we observed that differences in the layout of houses and the way a dataset was annotated can greatly affect the performance in activity recognition. The work presented here demonstrates that a suitable sequence feature set combined with the WSVM classifier achieve good improvement and efficiency over the traditional used methods.

KEYWORDS:

Smart homes; Activity recognition; Machine learning; Support Vector Machines; Weighted SVM.

BIOGRAPHY:

Dr. M'hamed Bilal ABIDINE received the B.S degree in Exact Sciences, Algiers, Algeria in 2002. Then the M.S, Magister and PhD degrees from the Faculty of Electronics and Computer Sciences, University of Sciences and Technology Houari Boumediene (USTHB), Algiers, Algeria, in 2007, 2010 and 2017, respectively. Currently, he is a Research Associate Professor at the Faculty of Electronics and Computer Sciences, USTHB. His research focuses is multi-disciplinary expertise combining Pattern Recognition, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Computer Vision, and novel sensor hardware to make devices and processes smarter. He has published several International papers on Machine Learning and a regular member in several research projects.

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